

Slime Molds

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THE 11TH INTERNATIONAL CONGRESS
ON THE SYSTEMATICS AND ECOLOGY OF MYXOMYCETES

ABSTRACT BOOK

28-31 AUGUST 2023, TARTU, ESTONIA

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The International Congress on the Systematics and Ecology of Myxomycetes is the largest triannual meeting of the slime mould research community. It traditionally brings together scientists, amateurs, teachers and artists from around the globe fascinated by myxomycetes.

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Lime in Physarales. Morphological aspects

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Keywords: Physarales, lime, stacking techniques

In multicellular organisms, fungi, animals and plants, the morphology is determined by a precise assembly plan in which practically every detail is the result of natural selection. This close link between morphology and functionality justifies the prevalent use of morphological aspects in the taxonomy. In the case of myxomycetes, on the other hand, the morphology of the sporocarps is not determined by a precise assembly plan, but rather by the outcome of a series of coordinated processes and by the influence of environmental conditions. These processes are certainly the result of natural selection, but not all of their outcomes, often even the most obvious, must necessarily be. This has sometimes led a taxonomy based solely on morphological aspects, without the identification of the processes that had determined them, on the wrong path. This was particularly true in the case of Physarales as regards the presence of limes in the sporocarps. The extensive use of photographic stacking techniques that allows to obtain high resolution optical images can suggest hypotheses on the links between morphological aspects and formation processes and pose questions to which the literature does not seem to have given exhaustive answers. This work has focused the attention on the link between peridium and capillitium in Physaraceae, on the structure of the calcareous stipe in Physarales, with a brief mention on the cortex in the genus *Fuligo*.

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Quantifying the unseen: a novel qPCR approach to measure myxomycete biomass in soil substrate

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Myxomycetes are a diverse group of amoeboid protists that inhabit various terrestrial environments and have been extensively studied for their taxonomic diversity. However, despite their prevalence and abundance in soil ecosystems, there is still limited knowledge about their growth behaviour as plasmodia in soil substrate and their capability to establish themselves in soil over time. This study aims to explore the growth of four Myxomycetes species in artificial soil substrate. Our primary objectives are to determine whether plasmodia, when inoculated as sclerotia into the substrate, can develop and grow in such an environment. To achieve this, we have developed a qPCR-based approach to quantitatively measure and monitor the growth of Myxomycetes biomass over a period of at least one month. By doing so, we aim to elucidate the temporal dynamics of Myxomycetes biomass in soil. Overall, this study will shed light on the potential of Myxomycetes plasmodia to grow and establish themselves in a complex soil environment.

The Myxomycetes collection of Meise Botanic Garden

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Keywords: Digitization, Herbarium, Myxogastria

Meise Botanic Garden (MBG) celebrated its 225th anniversary in 2022. At the start in 1797 it was a small teaching garden located in the center of Brussels (Belgium), displaying a small collection of native and exotic plants. From then on the Garden kept expanding and became a scientific institution with a large living collection and herbarium. In 1938 it was moved to its actual location just outside Brussels in the community of Meise (Flanders).

The herbarium of MBG (BR) holds 4 million collection items and in this poster we focus the myxomycete collections that count over 35.000 specimens, from all over the world, including more than 300 type specimens, making this one of the bigger myxomycetes collections worldwide. In this poster we provide “dry” numbers like the oldest specimens are dated 1825, along with some “fun facts”, such as: these oldest specimens are part of the J. d’Udekem herbarium who was family of Belgium’s current Queen Mathilde.

Although the specimens are kept with great care by our herbarium staff, they are showing signs of degradation. It is crucial that specimens are preserved and protected from further deterioration, and still keep their morphological data accessible for study, we therefore have started to re-examine the most valuable specimens (e.g. types, rare species, historically important specimens, etc.) and make a complete documentation of each that will be made available in PDF format for all on the MYXO-BE website managed by MBG. In addition, a sample will be preserved of every examined specimen for molecular analysis.

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Additions to the knowledge of Myxomycetes in Maize fields

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Keywords: Agriculture, biocontrol, corn, *Dictyostelium*, *Myxobacteria*, *Myxogastria*

Following the studies of the potential use of myxomycetes as Biocontrol Agents on agricultural crops such as maize (*Zea mays*) in test fields of campus Tulln of the University of Natural Resources (Austria) (Lemmens & de Haan 2017) an extensive survey selected maize fields in Flanders (Belgium) was done in 2020 and 2021.

We investigated whether there is a difference in myxomycetes species composition among different parts of the corn plant (Mironova et al. 2023). Moist chamber cultures (MCCs) were set up using different parts of the corn plant (male inflorescence, green leaf, corn cob leaf, silks, aerial leaf litter and ground leaf litter). We also explored the possible difference in species composition between samples collected from the center or the edge of the corn field. The MCCs of corn plant substrates allowed us to isolate six different species: *Didymium bahiense*, *D. difforme*, *D. squamulosum*, *Physarum gravidum*, *P. cinereum* and *Perichaena vermicularis*. During an exploratory survey, two additional species, *Echinostelium minutum* and *Perichaena liceoides*, were obtained in MCCs from ground leaf litter. Collecting in situ was done opportunistically and this yielded two species, *D. bahiense* and *P. gravidum*.

Lastly, it was investigated how to isolate myxomycetes from soil samples using weak malt yeast agar (wMY) and sterilized leaf litter. No myxomycetes were isolated from the soil samples, although young plasmodia were observed, but these did not develop further. Sorocarps of *Dictyostelium sphaerocephalum*, a cellular slime mould (Dictyostelia), were observed in wMY agar cultures of soil samples.

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Myxomycetes of the Mayotte archipelago (France)

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Keywords: Africa, islands, Indian Ocean, species inventory, Myxogastria

In this poster we present new data of myxomycetes inventorization of the Mayotte archipelago. The island group of Mayotte of volcanic origin, is located in the Mozambique Channel (Indian Ocean) between the southeast of the African continent and Madagascar.

More specimens, collected in the field and obtained in moist chamber cultures from the surveys held in 2010, 2011 and 2013, were added and critical specimens were reexamined. A total of 270 specimens have now been recorded, these represent 27 genera, 75 species and 7 infraspecific taxa (de Haan et al. 2023).

Arcyria glauca, *Cribraria* cf. *tecta* and *Hemitrichia aurea* reported for the first time from Africa. *Diderma rimosum*, *Macbrideola argentea* and *Physarum retisporum* represent second records for Africa.

Most of the collections (60%) were found on dead wood, second to this substrate is the coconut palm (*Cocos nucifera* L) with a yield of 21% among which *Diderma rimosum*, *Hemitrichia aurea*, *Physarum lakhampalii* and *Physarum superbum* as most note worthy recorded on this tree-like monocot.

A comparison of species lists of island (groups) in the region, such as La Réunion, Madagascar, Seychelles and Mayotte (Adamonyte et al. 2011, Wrigley de Basanta et al. 2012, Kryvomaz et al. 2017, 2020, de Haan et al. IN PRESS) shows that there are only 38 taxa (17%) in common. When comparing the complete species assemblage of the islands, with the total list of Eastern Africa there are 147 taxa (42%) in common. Both suggesting a considerable level of endemism.

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Diversity and persistence of nivicolous myxomycetes: Over 10 years research in a transect in the German Alps

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Keywords: nivicolous myxomycetes, long term research, ecological zonation

With a high dispersal capacity via airborne spores, myxomycetes can easily reach distant new sites. However, unlimited dispersal can be a two-edged blade for local genetic adaptation, if there is free immigration from non-adapted spores. Evolution may solve this problem, called outbreeding depression, by shifting to an apomictic mode of reproduction [1], reducing dispersal capabilities [2], or developing reproductive barriers between populations, which may lead to cryptic speciation [3]. We study this problem in nivicolous myxomycetes and conducted several case studies comparing geographically distant populations. However, we still know less about the genetic differentiation within a population, and the persistence of the genotypes composing it. Understanding reproductive strategies requires long-term monitoring of their population dynamics.

More than 1600 specimens have been collected at our transect site in the German Alps since 2013, with more than 80% successfully barcoded for partial sequences of the 18S rDNA. We found 121 ribotypes from 37 morphospecies, with one to ten ribotypes per morphospecies. The large gap between the number of morphotypes and ribotypes counted may indicate regional species differentiation. A phylogenetic tree constructed was consistent with these results, with a few exceptions. In addition to manual ribotype definition, a species delimitation algorithm (automatic barcode gap discovery [4]) was applied to the entire dataset. The algorithm yielded partitions that corresponded at a specific threshold almost exactly to the pre-determined morphotypes. Geographical coordinates confirmed that the same ribotype was collected repeatedly for a species between years, suggesting the existence of a persistent amoebal colony. On the other hand, no particular correlation between the occurrence of a ribotype/morphotype and environmental parameters was found. To find a fine-scale ecological zonation which refers to our classification, if existing at all, a multi-dimensional analysis is needed, using remotely sensed environmental data in addition to our records.

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Genetic variability of nivicolous myxomycetes in the Tatra Mountains (Carpathians) in the wide-range context of the group

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Keywords: diversity, local scale, nivicolous myxomycetes, SSU, Tatra Mts.

Nivicolous myxomycetes are a highly specialized ecological group of organisms associated with long-lasting snow cover. They occur disjunctly in all mountain massifs of the world where periodic snow is present. While many mountain ranges have been surveyed for myxomycetes and nearly 100 nivicolous species are described, their patterns of diversity and geographical distribution at both global and regional scales are still poorly understood. In particular, available data on genetic diversity are unevenly distributed and comprehensive surveys generally scarce. Here, we aimed to provide the first genetic diversity analysis of nivicolous myxomycetes from a poorly investigated yet biogeographically important area – the Tatra mountains (Carpathians), a key Central European high-mountain site. In the course of several field trips, around 950 herbarium specimens of 29 nivicolous species from 21 field sites were collected. All specimens were morphologically determined and subjected to the amplification of partial small ribosomal subunit (SSU) regarded as a barcode marker for myxomycetes. The obtained individual haplotypes were analysed in the context of the total intraspecific diversity of a given species available in the public database (GenBank). Preliminary results showed that almost all morphological species from the Tatra Mts were represented by more than one (mainly two or three) haplotypes. Most of them were identical with genetic variants known from other geographical regions. Our study indicates that most haplotypes of various nivicolous myxomycete species are widely distributed geographically. Our analysis was based on the SSU marker only as the only marker well represented in public genetic data repositories. To further understand the complex pattern of species diversity and distribution on a global scale, there is a need to systematically extend comprehensive genetic studies to other understudied areas and to include a wider molecular diversity screening by extending the barcoding marker system.

From nerdy to trendy - a brief history of myxomycetes and citizen science in Norway

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Keywords: Myxomycetes, citizen science, history, Norway

The history of collecting myxomycetes in Norway dates back to Linnaeus, Blytt and Sommerfelt. By 1860, the number of species known from Norway was about 70. Nobody worked systematically with myxomycetes until Astrid Karlsen, who was trained by Gulielma Lister, revised the Oslo Herbarium specimens and also collected extensively in Western Norway in the 1930s and 1940s (Karlsen 1934, 1943). By 1943 the number of species in Norway had increased to 100. In the 1980s, Johannesen (1982) and Kalstø (1985) studied myxomycetes and through their work the number of species increased to 198. Johannesen and Vetlesen (2020) published 130 species new to Norway and the number had increased to 363 by 2020. Today more than 400 species of myxomycetes have been reported from Norway.

Norway is a small country and the proportion of the approximately 1050 species described worldwide is surprisingly high, especially since so few people have been working actively with collecting and identifying myxomycetes in Norway until recently. In comparison, ca. 260 species are known from Sweden, a country where Uno Eliasson and several others have published papers on myxomycetes for many decades. Possible explanations for this difference, especially related to the interactions between taxonomists and citizen scientists and the availability of appropriate tools will be discussed.

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Citizen science as a key driver of myxomycete research in Latvia

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Keywords: myxomycetes, citizen science, observations, Latvia

Citizen science is well developed in Latvia, largely because of the nature observation portal dabasdati.lv, where anyone can report observations of all organism groups, including myxomycetes. Within the first ten years of the portal (2009-2019) there had been approximately 1600 observations of myxomycetes in total, with a little more than 100 reporters. Starting from 2016 the number of myxomycete reports in dabasdati.lv has gone from several hundred to a few thousand observations of myxomycetes per year. Up to the beginning of 2023 there have been more than 14000 observations of myxomycetes registered in the portal dabasdati.lv by 200 reporters with more than 200 observed taxa in total including more than 100 new taxa in Latvia. Citizen science has not only significantly contributed to the discovery of new species but also has given an opportunity for ecology studies. A large number of observations makes it possible to see the time of growth of myxomycete species. Some of the reporters have done research in local areas and so there are lists of species for different parts of Latvia and for areas of different sizes. This is a great example of how observation data can be used in myxomycete research and there is still a lot of potential to use this data as the basis for more research in the future.

***Licea pygmaea* in Australia grows in straight lines.**

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Keywords: Australia, Western Australia, Myxomycetes, Collaboration.

Fig. 1. Distribution of *Lycea pygmaea* in Australia according to www.discoverlife.org

Continental Australia is long isolated after the breakup of Gondwana, resulting in the evolution of a unique biota. Australia's flora is diverse, with 89 bioregions and a range of climatic zones; 70% of the land mass is arid, bordered by the northern tropics and the southern Mediterranean and colder climates, and including two biodiversity hotspots.

Myxomycete species are well represented in Australia with approximately one third of the known species, however many are represented by just a few records, and only 10 new species described to date. Through field collections and moist chamber harvesting, a curiosity-driven community within Australia are contributing to the myxomycete knowledge base. Outcomes of this research are somewhat *ad hoc*, but nonetheless very productive and laying a baseline foundation for understanding patterns in Australian myxomycete assemblages. West Australian research outcomes based on the author's holiday camping events are no less significant, leading to: increased understanding of the distribution of common species; new records for Australia; support for the general idea that a range of species are atypical and do not fit neatly into current species concepts; querying the species documented to occur in Australia; the discovery of species considered rare in the northern hemisphere commonly occur locally; the discovery of potential new species; and the description of new species, for example two unusual species recently described from arid regions in Western Australia, *Clastoderma confusum* and *Echinostelium australiense* (in press).

Current research indicates there are many more discoveries to be made. However, without myxomycologists in Australia or institutional assistance, collaboration with international experts is

essential, and more importantly, sought. It's time Australian myxomycetes become part of mainstream high-level research, in particular inclusion in phylogenetic studies. There is a small but eager community in Australia awaiting to hear from you!

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First systematic moist chamber study of myxomycetes on the island Hiddensee (Germany) demonstrates the arid nature of the myxomycete biota at the Baltic Sea coast

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Keywords: 18S rDNA, Protophysarum phloiogenum, xerophilic myxomycetes

Hiddensee is a small island in the Baltic Sea, located to the west of the island of Rügen. On the northeastern, hilly part of Hiddensee, the Dornbusch, a biological station of the University of Greifswald is located. During the period 8–13.11.2022, we sampled coastal heathlands and shrub-beries to collect substrates for a moist chamber experiment. Substrates for 103 moist chambers were collected, including leaf and branch litter of *Calluna vulgaris* (L.) Hull, aerial litter of *Sum-bucus nigra* L., bark of *Pinus sylvestris* L., *Crataegus monogyna* Jacq., *Acer campestre* L., and dung of sheep and cow. The moist chamber experiment lasted 55 days and yielded 117 collections, including several species rare in Germany, including *Protophysarum phloiogenum* M. Blackw. & Alexop., *Perichaena luteola* (Kowalski) Gilert, *Trichia munda* (Lister) Meyl., Bull. and *Diderma hemisphaericum* (Bull.) Hornem. The records of *P. phloiogenum* appear to be the first in Germany (Schnittler et al., 1996, 2011). We obtained a partial 18S rDNA sequence for one collection, which was most similar (95.3%) with a sequence from GenBank (Walker et al., 2003), probably from North America.

Physarales were the most diverse and abundant group for the studied substrates. Another peculiarity was the rapid development of fructifications: the first fruiting bodies appeared already on the 3rd day of the experiment, which is typical for myxomycete communities in arid zones (Schnittler, 2001). The climate of the Hiddensee is characterized by frequent, strong winds that may rapidly change direction, as well as sunny weather (about 1850 hours a year), with relatively modest precipitation (540 mm). Thus, the climate of the island can be characterized as rather dry, which is reflected in local myxomycete biota. In particular, the finding of *P. phloiogenum*, previously discovered in Mongolia, Kazakhstan, USA (Colorado and Arizona), Morocco, Russia (As-trakhan), South Australia and other arid regions, supports this supposition.

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Witches' vomit, spittle and butter: Slime molds in Latvian folk belief

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Keywords: folk belief, legends, slime molds, witch, witches' vomit

Throughout history, people have believed in witchcraft and witches in order to explain events or phenomena that they could not understand or control. The fear of the unknown and the need for explanation led people to blame witches and other supernatural forces for household misfortunes and productivity loss, illnesses etc. In my paper, by analyzing a corpus of about 150 Latvian beliefs and legend texts about so-called “witches' vomit”, “witches' spittle”, “witches' excrement”, and “witches' butter” I will analyze the link between these beliefs and various natural phenomena, including slime molds, and characterize the chronology, geographical distribution and other aspects of these beliefs.

The beliefs about witches' vomit, spittle, or excrement, as well as about witches' butter, relate to the oldest layer of Latvian witchcraft beliefs which existed before the mid-16th century when the wave of witch burning reached the territory of Latvia from central Europe, along with the character of diabolic witches defined by Christian demonology. It seems that the aforementioned folk terms referred to various natural phenomena – witches' spittle most probably designated the froth found on plants produced by spittlebugs, while slime molds and fungi were most likely referred to as witches' butter or witches' vomit. Without understanding the origin of these slimy substances that could suddenly appear on wooden structures, wooden household objects, or elsewhere on the premises, it was believed that they were left behind by witches for various reasons. A wide range of magical practices have been described in folk beliefs and legends, by means of which witches' vomit was destroyed – it was drown, burned, buried, rubbed, poked, etc. The appearance of these inexplicable, suspicious substances also caused social tension and conflicts among neighbors, which often manifested as both verbal and physical violence.

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Should we describe cryptic species of myxomycetes?

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Keywords: biospecies, morphospecies, reproductive isolation

The advances in molecular barcoding technology confronted myxomycete taxonomists with the problem of cryptic species. In virtually all case studies undertaken so far, a morphologically circumscribed species turned out to be composed of several genetic lineages, which may show subtle morphological differences (*Hemitrichia serpula*, Dagamac et al. 2017) or not (*Trichia varia*, Schnittler & Feng 2015). Analysis of two or more independently inherited molecular markers reveals that such lineages are reproductively isolated and therefore can be seen as biological species (Shchepin et al. 2022). Such closely related species do not necessarily show phenotypic differences between each other, since this requires either (1) selection pressure on visually identifiable characters, or (2) a ‘fortunate’ course of gene drift, which will lead to the random accumulation of morphological traits. Therefore, phenotypic recognisability does not necessarily evolve at the same time as genetic, ecological or physiological divergences (De Queroz, 2007), which may cause disagreements between morphologically discernible and really existing species. In comparison to not-spore-forming organisms, speciation in myxomycetes may be stimulated by an additional factor. Populations accumulate special adaptations to their local habitat but migrating spores of the same species come from distant locations and bring alleles with adaptations to other conditions. This phenomenon, known as outbreeding depression, can be avoided by establishing reproductive barriers. The ability to do so may have a long evolutionary history in myxomycetes and become rather effective in their extant lineages. The question arises: should we formally describe species, if molecular data indicate the existence of several independent species, but morphological differences between them are (yet) unknown? The following arguments can be raised against this.

(1) If two species cannot be distinguished morphologically, their identification is impossible within standard studies of biodiversity, ecology, and geography. Therefore, when describing cryptic species, we will give them names that are unlikely to be used by most researchers interested in biodiversity and/or ecology. This will increase the information noise, bear the risk of miscommunication and devalue the species as a taxonomic unit. Molecular barcoding of every accession will be the only way out of this dilemma.

(2) Valid species descriptions include a diagnosis that provides clear phenotypic differences from other species. For cryptic species, the diagnosis can only be based on nucleotide sequences, which goes against established practices, at least in botany.

(3) Molecular methods have limitations. As an example, the lack of interbreeding, which is widely used to prove reproductive isolation, may instead be caused by the geographical isolation of populations, which belong to the same species. Therefore, it is advisable to wait for a methodology that can reliably demonstrate reproductive barriers before describing cryptic species. The barcoding gap principle, which works well in some myxomycete groups, fails in others.

(4) It is unclear what to do with apomictic (asexual) lines, which may be present in myxomycetes, and sometimes have a distinct morphology, like *Didymium ovoideum*. They are reproductively isolated from related sexual lines, but do not form coherent reproductive groups, as biological species do. If an apomictic line becomes genetically heterogeneous, i.e. by occasional cross-breeding with sexual lineages, it can be subdivided into "species" ad infinitum (a situation we have in many apomictic groups of vascular plants).

The main arguments in support of describing cryptic species run as follows.

(1) Cryptic species really exist, and the task of science is to describe reality, not just a convenient fraction of it. Describing only those species that are easy to distinguish from each other is an anthropocentric simplification of reality, which cannot be accepted in science.

(2) Different cryptic species may show a distinct ecology and distribution. Using the same name for all of them results in analysing the biological properties of an artificial construct. Complexes of morphologically identical or similar species cannot have a defined ecological niche, range, or phenology; they also cannot be effectively conserved. Using them as operational units will lead to wrong biological generalizations, such as the recently refuted idea of the ubiquity of spore-forming organisms.

(3) With advances in science, formerly cryptic species may become morphologically discernible. In future, new sets of characters may become accessible, while already known but sophisticated methods may become more routine.

(4) Biological nomenclature does not provide any other marking of species than the assignment of a Latin epithet. Indexes like 'a1' or 'gt1' are not regulated by any rules, and will differ from publication to publication. The only way to ensure unambiguous names is to formally describe new species according to the rules of nomenclature.

(5) The current rapid biodiversity decline does not leave time for elaborate, time-consuming methods of traditional taxonomy. Species may become extinct faster than they can be described.

(6) What can be done will be done sooner or later. We thus should not ignore the possibility of describing cryptic species but should develop algorithms and practices for this task already.

The description of cryptic species has already become a routine practice in the taxonomy of algae, fungi, heterotrophic protists. In prokaryotic microbiology, description by molecular signatures is widely used not only for species but also for higher taxa, up to divisions and kingdoms, even when the organism is only identifiable through metagenomic data. For myxomycetes, the question remains open; up to date no strictly cryptic species has been described in this group. The authors invite colleagues to open a broad discussion on this topic.

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What is *Lycogala fuscoviolaceum*?

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Keywords: holotype, aethalium, pseudocapillitium, Reticulariaceae

In 1968, the Danish mycologist P. Onsberg received from his student a single interesting specimen of *Lycogala*, collected in the highlands of Nepal. In 1972, after consulting with G.W. Martin, Onsberg described a new species, *L. fuscoviolaceum* (Onsberg 1972). According to the original description, the species differs from *L. epidendrum* in its dark-brown spore mass, a very dense peridium, and the pseudocapillitium forming vertically oriented bunches.

After Onsberg's work, no one ever found *L. fuscoviolaceum* again. To understand what this species represents, we examined its holotype, which is still kept in Copenhagen. Thorough examination of the author's collection showed that the material does not belong to the genus *Lycogala*. The fruiting bodies form convex, multilayer clusters rather than flat colonies as in other species of *Lycogala*. The peridium has a cartilaginous texture and an alveolar structure reminiscent of *Siphoptychium violaceum*. The pseudocapillitium consists of stiff membranous strands resembling the columella of *Siphoptychium*, but as well the pseudocapillitium found in *Reticularia*. The structure of the peridium and pseudocapillitium indicate that the fruiting bodies of *L. fuscoviolaceum* are aethalia, whereas in other species of the genus *Lycogala*, according to recent data, they are sporocarps. The spores of *L. fuscoviolaceum* are rather unusual, they are thick-walled, slightly oval, and ornamented with a fine network, which has remarkably wide borders.

All these characteristics indicate that *L. fuscoviolaceum* is either a myxomycete from the family Reticulariaceae, close to *Siphoptychium* or *Reticularia* (as indicated by the structure of the fruiting body), or it is not a myxomycete at all (what can be concluded from the unusual spore ornamentation). Molecular studies will hopefully help to determine the taxonomic affiliation of this interesting specimen.

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A Taxonomic Klondike: *Lycogala epidendrum* represents the largest species complex among Myxomycetes known thus far

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Keywords: biospecies, new taxa, Reticulariaceae

Lycogala epidendrum (L.) Fr. is one of the first protists ever discovered and the first myxomycete described by botanists. Being considered as a very familiar object, in many cases *L. epidendrum* was not even collected during field research. In a series of studies conducted from 2019 to 2023, we have found that the morphological species *L. epidendrum* represents a polyphyletic taxonomic complex. It consists of at least 76 reproductively isolated, but in many cases co-occurring clades, which we consider as biological species (these data are partially published in Leontyev et al. 2022a).

Morphological differences were observed between the biospecies, detected by molecular methods, with the peridial vesicles emerging as particularly significant structures. Single crystals, star-like druses, oil droplets, granular accumulations, and pigment deposits were found inside them. The presence of these structures, as well as the shape and mutual arrangement of vesicles, allow to distinguish biospecies from one another (Leontyev et al. 2022b).

In 2023, 15 new species of the genus *Lycogala* were formally described, for which a sufficient number of well-preserved specimens, collected from different locations, was available. Among them there are *L. roseosporum* with a pink spore mass and black vesicles, *L. olearium* with oily deposits in the vesicles, *L. caviaroides*, in which the vesicles resemble dried red caviar, and *L. leopardium*, in which the vesicles contain druses of crystals (Leontyev et al. 2023). Other species, discovered by molecular methods, but not described among these first fifteen, also possess distinctive morphological features. For instance, *L. tigrinum* ad int. has a striped peridium, *L. umbrinum* ad int. displays dark umber-pink coloration of the sporocarp, while *L. rufosporum* ad int. has a brick-red spore mass.

To describe the entire diversity of species still hidden under the name *L. epidendrum*, much more collections are needed, particularly from less-explored areas such as East Asia, Africa, and South America. A thrilling question is if the limited number of morphological traits available for the group will allow to characterise unambiguously all species by a unique combination of these traits.

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Will nivicolous myxomycetes respond to climate change?

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Keywords: species distribution modeling, Lamproderma, ecological niche

Nivicolous myxomycetes are not a homogeneous group in their fruiting phenology (Ronikier & Ronikier, 2009) and comprise (i) strictly nivicolous species (fructify in high altitudes, mostly in alpine-subalpine regions) (ii) facultatively nivicolous species (form fruiting bodies both in mountains and on plains), and cryophilic species (occur also in autumn and during winter thaws). The ecological requirements of the last group are least known.

Ecological niche modelling has not been widely used in studies of myxomycetes; there are only a few examples of the application of this methodology to certain species (Dagamac et al., 2021; Rojas et al., 2015). Using machine learning methods, I attempt to identify the ecological requirements of each subgroup. Based on the built model I made a prediction according to the projections of climate change scenarios from global climate models (GCM).

As the study object *Lamproderma* genus was chosen as it contains representatives of all ecological subgroups that are distributed in temperate and boreal parts of Europe. I used data of 2 representative species from each subgroup as follows: *L. ovoideum*, *L. aeneum* - strictly nivicolous species; *L. pseudomaculatum*, *L. splendens* - facultatively nivicolous species; *L. arcyrioides*, *L. sauteri* - cryophilous species.

Among the methods, the Random Forest had the best performance and biologically meaningful models. Among the bioclimatic factors most important were Temperature Seasonality, Precipitation of the Driest Month, and Mean Temperature of the Driest Quarter, which captures the basic bioclimatic requirements mostly at the amoeba stage (amount of soil moisture, long snow cover during the winter). Under an “optimistic” scenario, all three groups will be able to expand to the lowlands; under the scenario of the continued growth of emissions, species can form refuges in the mountains and completely disappear from the lowlands.

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The checklist of Myxomycetes in Ukraine: the next level

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Keywords: checklist, GBIF, Ukraine, occurrence, literature

In 1834, the first confirmed discovery of myxomycetes species in Ukraine was made by the French mycologist J.H. Léveillé (Léveillé 1842). Throughout the long history of myxomycete research in Ukraine, various state systems led to scientific works being written in different languages, mainly Ukrainian, Russian, and Polish. Considerable part of these publications are only available in printed form, as a rare editions kept in a few libraries.

In 2005 and 2009, efforts were made by D. Leontyev and T. Kryvomaz to improve the available data, but they primarily focused on the species list formation, with the detailed occurrences remaining unseen. A critical reassessment of the locality data on the of myxomycete finds was initiated by I. Dudka and D. Leontyev in 2015, but the project was put on hold due to I. Dudka's death in 2017.

Our objective is to reconstruct the data spanning over 180 years of myxomycetes research in Ukraine and create a comprehensive checklist, which includes detailed geographic data. This checklist aims to provide valuable information for ecological studies, particularly for assessing the impact of the Russian aggression against Ukraine on the biodiversity of the country.

As a source of data we used monographs, peer-reviewed journals, and conference abstracts. The taxonomic assessment was based on various nomenclature databases and expert opinions. Occurrences lacking coordinates were georeferenced using text descriptions or digitizing available maps. The datasets were subject to quality control, including data cleaning and misspelling checks. The Checklist dataset was automatically derived from the Occurrence dataset after taxonomic assessment and data cleaning.

The datasets are ready to be openly published to GBIF and offer valuable insights into myxomycetes occurrences in Ukraine and contain more than 4200 evidence records of 321 accepted species. These datasets provide a foundation for ecological research and will contribute to biodiversity management efforts.

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***Tasmaniomyxa umbilicata*, a new genus and new species of myxomycete from areas surrounding the Tasman Sea**

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Key words: Gondwana, morphology, phylogeny, sporocarp development.

A new genus and species of dark-spored myxomycete, *Tasmaniomyxa umbilicata* ad int., will be described based on numerous observations in Tasmania and additional records from south eastern Australia and New Zealand. The new taxon is characterized by the following characters. Sporocarps are stalked; sporotheca is globose to wide ovoid, umbilicate at the base. Stalk subulate, black. Peridium single, membranous, breaking at the apex into 6–8 petaloid lobes. Columella cylindrical, opaque, with a jagged edge. Capillitium flaccid, firmly attached both to the columella and peridium. Capillitial threads white in mass, tubular, poorly branching, with occasional nodes and funnel-shaped tips. Spores irregularly verrucose. Plasmodium yellow.

The new taxon is characterized by an unusual combination of characters from two families: Lamprodermataceae and Didymiaceae. With Lamprodermataceae the species shares limeless sporocarps, a shining membranous peridium, an epihypothallic stalk and a cylindrical columella. Like Didymiaceae, it has a soft, flaccid, sparsely branched capillitium, with rough tubular threads that contain fusiform nodes and are firmly connected to the peridium. Other characters of *T. umbilicata* that also occur in many Didymiaceae are the peridium dehiscing into petaloid lobes, the yellow, motile plasmodium, and the spores ornamented with larger grouped and smaller scattered warts. Principal Component Analysis, conducted using a feature table of dark-spored taxa, shows that *T. umbilicatum* occupies an isolated position between two large complexes: (1) species with limeless sporocarps and a rigid, solid capillitium and (2) species with calcareous sporocarps and a soft, tubular capillitium. The transitional position of the new taxon is also supported by a three-gene phylogeny, which places *T. umbilicata* at the base of the branch of all lime-containing Physarales, thus justifying its description as a genus.

What is *Lamproderma*? A three-gene phylogeny

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Keywords: Lamprodermataceae, SSU, EF1A, COI

With ca. 60 described species, the genus *Lamproderma* Rostaf. is one of the most diverse within *Myxomycetes*. It is well circumscribed by a combination of morphologic characters: stalked sporocarps (so-called sporangia), a sporotheca covered by an iridescent, membranous peridium, and threads of the capillitium ending in acute tips. Related genera can be told apart by the absence of stalk and columella (*Diacheopsis* Meyl.), whereas others develop waxy substances that may persist or not after sporocarps completely mature (*Elaeomyxa* Hagelst. and *Colloderma* G. Lister, respectively).

Unfortunately, as it has happened with many other groups of organisms, molecular studies disproved this concept: *Lamproderma* is not a monophyletic genus (Fiore-Donno et al., 2012; Leontyev et al., 2019). Phylogenies include, at least, four different genera: *Lamproderma*, *Elaeomyxa*, *Colloderma*, and *Diacheopsis*. In order to disentangle the phylogeny of *Lamproderma* and its allied genera included in the family *Lamprodermataceae*, barcodes of three different molecular markers (SSU, EF1A, and COI) have been obtained. The respective phylogenies will be used to suggest a new classification within the *Lamprodermataceae*, and will supplement the morphological studies of the traditional genus *Lamproderma*, such as those performed by Moreno et al. (2002) or Ronikier (2022).

First results revealed that characters like the mottled peridium are artificial, since the species do not create a monophyletic group. Similarly, the loss of the stalk in the taxa united in the genus *Diacheopsis* seems to be a result of multiple convergent evolution. In addition, the molecular diversity of morphologically circumscribed species varies by nearly one order of magnitude, and complexes of cryptic species are likely to occur.

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Molecular and behavioral ecological approaches reveal a self - non-self recognition (allorecognition) in Myxomycetes

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Keyword: plasmodium, allorecognition, behavior, *Physarum rigidum*, self – non-self recognition

It is well known that plasmodium of Myxomycetes can fuse with other individuals of the same species (Figure 1a), but even among intraspecies, plasmodium is generally unable to fuse with most other individuals (Figure 1b). Plasmodium is able to accurately determine whether or not an individual it encounters is a target for fusion and selects "fusion or not" behavior; this ability is a kind of allorecognition.

According to previous researches, two plasmodia can fuse only if they are phenotypically identical for the loci to fuse. The recognition is not only possible by contact between cell membranes, but also by contact only with the slime sheath. However, the details of the genes and signal substances are not known. Thus, the whole view of allorecognition behavior in Myxomycetes is not well understood. To elucidate the mechanisms of allorecognition, it is important to understand the genes, signal substances, and behaviors that are involved in recognition. This study aims to solve these challenges by using molecular and behavioral ecological approaches with *Physarum rigidum* and *Physarum roseum*.

To identify the genes involved in allorecognition, we will conduct spatial transcriptome analysis for plasmodium. Currently, we are preparing transcriptome and genome references for analysis.

In order to identify the signal substances, we conducted behavioral tests, between different species to narrow down the screening targets. The results showed that the allorecognition behavior observed among intraspecies was not observed between interspecies (Figure 1c). It suggests that the signal substances were species-specific.

To understand the significance of allorecognition behavior, we conducted behavioral tests using plasmodium that were collected in a single field. As the results, complexity exists in combinations that were possible or impossible to fusion within a single field.

Fig. 1. Three typical cases of allorecognition. (a) Fusion case: There are rare combinations that can be fused if they are of the same species. (b) Avoidance case: Avoid each other in most cases, even among intraspecies. (c) Ignore case: Different species of plasmodium ignore each other.

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What is *Comatricha suksdorfii*?

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Key words: nivicolous myxomycetes; species delimitation; type collections

The problems of many species described in the 19th century are varied. In the first place, the very reduced morphological description, with hardly any microscopic data, which makes it very difficult to interpret them nowadays. The lack of material preserved in official herbaria and, when present, the shortage of it. Finally, the difficulty to use this material in molecular studies.

Minimal invasive techniques such as SEM study with the critical point technique mean that with few spores and a small part of a sporocarp we can establish its microscopic characteristics up to 10,000 times magnification.

Once their macro- and microscopic differences are known, we can compare them with other similar species. This has been the case of a nivicolous species: *Comatricha suksdorfii* Ellis & Everh., Bull. Washburn Lab. Nat.Hist. 1:5 (1884). We compare our samples with the holotype of the species (NY 5310), and thus we can differentiate two very clear morphological species. The first present in Spain, very abundant in the mountains of Sierra de Guadarrama National Park, which we define as *Comatricha appendiculata* and we differentiate it from a close species *C. calderaensis*, also nivicolous, and the American species, also nivicolous, which we provisionally name *Comatricha americana*.

Finally, we propose a key to differentiate the nivicolous species of *Comatricha* known so far.

Studies of Myxomycetes in Belarus

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Keywords: myxomycetes, biodiversity, National Park, reserves, Belarus

For a long time Myxomycetes were a poorly studied on the territory of Belarus. Chronologically, the studies of the group can be divided into three periods. The first is the end of the 19th and the beginning of the 20th centuries associated with the work of Polish and Russian researchers (Twardowska, 1885; Yachevsky, 1907; Kastory, 1912; Lebedeva, 1925a, 1925b, 1935). 50 species of myxomycetes have been identified. The second is the end of the 20th century (Serzhanina, Gapienko, 1980; Moroz, Novozhilov, 1987, 1994; Moroz, Dorozhkin, 1994; Shukanov, Moroz, Malinovsky, 1987; Moroz, 1991, 1993, 1996a, 1996b). From 1984 to 1996 90 species of myxomycetes have been identified. Third - from 2017 to the present, 64 species have been discovered and 26 scientific publications on myxomycetes from Belarus have been published. The list of myxomycetes in Belarus is represented by 205 species belonging to 47 genera, 13 families, 8 orders. During field collections, 132 species were identified, 30 species - by the method of "moist chamber", 43 species were identified both in field collections and in a moist chamber. For the first time, 155 species were noted on the territory of Belarus. Studies on the study of the biodiversity of myxomycetes were carried out both in specially protected natural areas: in the National Parks: "Narochansky", "Belovezhskaya Pushcha", "Pripyatsky", "Braslav Lakes", in the "Berezinsky Biosphere Reserve", in the biosphere reserve "Pribuzhskoe Polesie", in the reserves: "Vydritsa", "Lipichanskaya Pushcha", "Mozyr Ravines", "Yukhnovsky", "Prilepsky", "Glebkovka", "Volmyansky", "Stiklevo", "Naliboksky", "Gayno-Brodnya", "Svislochsko- Berezinsky", "Priluksky", "Central Botanical Garden of the National Academy of Sciences of Belarus", and in typical forest types for Belarus: pine forests, spruce forests, oak forests, black alder forests, aspen forests. Currently, the collection of myxomycetes includes more than 4,000 herbarium specimens.

Feasibility of using *Physarum polycephalum* microplasmoidal biomass as a feed for *Artemia* enrichment

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Keywords: Artemia enrichment, Artemia franciscana, Physarum polycephalum, slime molds

Artemia is a vital part of the diet for shrimp and fish larvae, but its nutritional value can be enhanced through costly and difficult to produce supplements such as DHA Selco and fresh microalgae. *Physarum polycephalum*, a slime mold with high protein and lipid content, is a potential candidate for use in dietary supplements. This study aimed to investigate the feasibility of using *P. polycephalum* microplasmoidal biomass as a feed for *Artemia franciscana*. Newly-hatched *Artemia nauplii* were enriched in five diet treatments, including DHA Selco, dry and fresh *P. polycephalum* microplasmoidal biomass, and mixtures of Selco with dry and fresh *P. polycephalum* biomass. The highest protein content and total carotenoids were found in the Selco mix with fresh *P. polycephalum* treatment. Dry *P. polycephalum* had the second highest protein content but the lowest carotenoids value. While Selco-fed *Artemia* had significantly higher lipid content than *Artemia* enriched with dry or fresh *P. polycephalum* biomass, there were no significant differences between Selco and the other two treatments. Based on these findings, *P. polycephalum* biomass could be a promising alternative feed for *Artemia* enrichment.

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Antioxidant and cytotoxicity activities of purified intracellular polysaccharides of *Physarum polycephalum*

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Keywords: Microplasmodia, Polysaccharides, Anion exchange chromatography, Antioxidant activity, Cytotoxicity, Slime molds

Myxomycetes are also called slime molds because their plasmodia often produce noticeable amounts of slime track (consisting mainly of exopolysaccharides) which can be visible on solid surfaces. Our previous studies found that polysaccharides including exopolysaccharides of *Physarum polycephalum* possess some remarkable biological activities. Thus, the main purpose of this study was to initially purify the crude intracellular polysaccharides (crIPSs) of this slime mold, then evaluate the antioxidant activity and anti-proliferative effect on cancer cell lines of the purified IPSs.

The total amount of crIPSs obtained from the 5-day-old microplasmodia of *P. polycephalum* was 0.2153 ± 0.043 (g/g dried biomass). The crIPSs were fractionated using a DEAE-cellulose column with Tris-HCl buffer and different NaCl concentrations (0.3 M, 0.4 M, and 0.6 M). Three fractions (F0.3, F0.4, and F0.6) were obtained with the content of 18.24%, 22.38%, and 11.64%, respectively. Regarding the antioxidant activity, only the F0.3 fraction showed radical scavenging activity with the IC₅₀ value of 24.766 (mg/mL). This activity was significantly lower than that of the standard, vitamin C (IC₅₀ of 25.245 μ g/mL). In terms of cytotoxicity, solely F0.6 fraction (1000 μ g/mL) demonstrated noticeable proliferative inhibition toward the tested cell lines with the inhibition rate of 50.79% and 54.78% on MCF-7, and HeLa cell lines, respectively. These proliferative inhibition activities are the same as that of the positive control, camptothecin. It should be noted that the F0.6 was not toxic to normal cells; the percentage of cell viability of fibroblast cells was 91.54% when treated with the same concentration of F0.6 as treated with the cancer cell lines. This suggested that cell inhibition of F0.6 seems to be selective, which is one of the promising traits and is worth further study.

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Preliminary results on the phylogeny and phenotypical traits evolution of genus *Cribraria*

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Keywords: *Cribrariaceae*, *SEM*, *taxonomy*, *nrSSU*

Cribrariaceae is an early-diverging family of bright-spored *Myxomycetes*, characterized by the presence of dictydine granules, while a true capillitium is lacking. Most species produce conspicuously stalked sporocarps with a netted peridium, which pattern is of major taxonomic importance. Ca. 50 species are currently accepted, but most taxonomic treatments agree on the difficulties of separating some morphologically close taxa. In addition, its systematics has largely been neglected in recent studies on *Myxomycetes*. As a result, the generic and species boundaries, as well as the evolution of phenotypic traits, have never been analysed in detail, especially not in a phylogenetic context with modern techniques.

Since very few DNA sequences of *Cribrariaceae* are available in public databases, and only of two DNA regions, viz., the nuclear small ribosomal subunit (nrSSU) and the elongation factor (EF), one of the objectives of the project is to generate additional molecular data on this group, also exploring, in the process, other DNA regions. These will be used to evaluate the taxonomic boundaries and reconstruct the phylogenetic relationships of the different species.

We will further perform a detailed morphological study and assess the evolution of certain phenotypic traits, within a phylogenetic context, such as the degree of development of the stalk and the calyculus, or the characters of the peridial net, including the differentiation of the nodes. Using scanning electron microscopy, we will further investigate those characters that cannot be properly observed with the usual light microscopy techniques, with special emphasis on the spore ornamentation.

Slime Molds (the journal) in numbers

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Keywords: citizen science, communication strategy, divulgation, open access

During the 10th International Congress on the Systematics and Ecology of Myxomycetes in Costa Rica in 2020, the late Dr. Indira Kalyanasundaram proposed developing an informal journal for myxomycetes and other slime molds. Seventeen months later, in July 2021, the first volume of “Slime Molds: An International Journal of Mycetozoans” (ISSN: 2215-650X) was published. With three complete volumes up to July 2023, this journal has already posted over 40 individual contributions on myxomycetes and dictyostelids. In this presentation, we communicate some of the numbers associated with the use of the website, including total downloads, individual connections, and number of countries where the information from the journal has been accessed. We also discuss, briefly, the origin of the contributions and the potential impact that citizen science initiatives such as this one can have on the development of scientific disciplines that grow primarily around academic activities.

Importance of including type specimens in phylogenetic studies of myxomycetes for proper interpretation of species characteristics and taxonomic boundaries

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Keywords: morphology, myxomycetes, phylogeny, type collections, taxonomy

Type collections are specimens based on which the species' name can be correctly applied, thus they are reference materials. Their correct interpretation is of key importance for understanding the species characteristics and defining species boundaries. Morphological revisions of type specimens over decades of myxomycete research have already shown that in some cases species have been interpreted inconsistently with their original concept. Sometimes, however, morphological examination of type specimens may be insufficient due to possible subjective interpretations of morphological features. Thus, there is an urgent need to revise type specimens of myxomycetes using modern techniques (SEM studies, DNA analyses) to obtain the appropriate reference for each species. Without a direct reference to the type specimen, phylogenetic position of any species is only an approximation. To fill this gap, we initiated a series of studies focused on type specimen collections in order to generate a foundation for a reliable and comprehensive, type-based phylogeny and analysis of evolutionary pathways in myxomycetes. First, we developed a non-destructive sampling of material for DNA analyses which allows us to overcome herbarium regulations that usually prohibit destructive sampling from type collections. Secondly, we initiated series of studies on type specimens of species from various genera based on morphological and molecular data. Our results show that: (1) it is possible to regularly obtain reliable barcode sequences from a portion of spores sampled from type specimens that were collected during last 30 years, (2) some morphologically similar species may represent separate taxa, (3) some morphologically distinguished species may be only variants of the same species, (4) molecular data are not sufficient for recognition of a given species, careful morphological examination of a specimen is always necessary. In conclusion, reconstruction of a modern phylogeny is only reliable when it takes into account sequences of type specimens.

Species descriptions in myxomycetes – can we settle on rules for good taxonomic practice?

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Keywords: best practice, species description, recommendations

The recent advances in molecular barcoding methods, but as well in photographic techniques, which now allow taking pictures with a high resolution directly in the field, led to a renewed interest in myxomycete taxonomy. Therefore, the trend of increasing numbers of new species described per year (Schnittler & Mitchell 2000) is likely to continue. This always bears the risk of premature descriptions, which later have to be synonymized with an existing species. This work substantially depletes the already limited resources of taxonomists, moreover, resulting in less cited and more conflict-prone publications. Fortunately, we have the Nomen Eumycetozoa database (2005–2023, <https://eumycetozoa.com>) as a taxonomic reference. Nevertheless, the development and regular updating of “a taxonomist cookbook” would benefit the taxonomy of myxomycetes by minimizing the risk of creating superfluous descriptions. This contribution tries to come up with a number of suggestions to open a discussion.

What makes myxomycetes special in comparison to other groups of organisms when it comes to the description of species new to science? Several features can be invoked. (1) In contrast to more complex organisms, myxomycete fructifications show only a limited set of morphological traits (but still more than many other groups of protists). This prompts us to explore the set of accessible characters as much as possible. (2) Myxomycete fructifications form not out of a growth process, but of a reformation of the already existing biomass of a plasmodium within a short time, usually hours to days. External factors at that time can alter characters a lot and increase phenotypic variability, as shown for the formation of lime scales (*Diderma tigrinum*, Ronikier et al. 2022). (3) Evolutionary changes in conspicuous characters, like the presence vs. absence of a stalk, or solitary vs. compound fructifications, seem to occur in myxomycetes frequently, which raised doubts about the monophyly of many traditionally accepted genera. (4) Many species of myxomycetes cannot be cultivated easily, so most of the studies are based on field specimens, which develop under non-standard conditions (this also applies to the moist chamber cultures). This complicates both the morphological descriptions and the experimental demonstration of reproductive isolation. (5) No universal primers for the molecular barcodes are available for myxomycetes. Most marker genes are very variable (18S rDNA, EF1a), some even too variable to be used in taxonomy (ITS). Mitochondrial genes in myxomycetes function based on insertional RNA editing, thus complicating the prediction of the protein reading frame.

What can be recommended for the description of a new species?

(1) The new species should be known from more than one collection, and from more than one locality. This reduces the opportunity to describe a taxon based on phenotypic aberrations but helps as well to assess the variation in morphological and molecular characters. Single accessions with a new combination of morphological characters appearing to be a good candidate for a new taxon can be pictured and described informally in a specialized journal like *Slime Molds* (<https://www.slimemolds.org>), or images can be posted on the internet, like in myxomycete appreciation group on Facebook, to raise attention which can bring in further observations.

(2) Describe the new taxon as comprehensively as possible, including as well its ecology and phenology. This enhances the chance to find this species again. Try to take images from the field and document as well immature stages, especially plasmodium colour, which can be helpful (like in *Tubifera* spp., see Leontyev et al. 2015). Provide coordinates of the collection site, as well as a photo and description of the macro- and microhabitat.

(3) Obtain a barcode from at least a single genetic marker for the new species, best sequence it for two or more independently inherited markers. This will allow proving if the accessions of the new taxon form indeed a monophyletic group. Having more markers increases the resolution of the phylogenetic analysis.

(4) Check, describe and discuss morphological differences to all related and already described taxa. If your new species is not cryptic, i.e. morphologically differs from the similar taxa, the new taxon should differ in at least one qualitative character. Quantitative characters, like differences in spore size of 0.5–1 µm, can be within the range of intraspecific variation (Woyzichowski et al. 2022).

(5) Check, describe and discuss molecular differences of the new species to the already described taxa. First do a BLAST search to identify related taxa (see recommendations by Kirschner et al. 2023). Then calculate the barcode gap, to ensure that it is well above the barcode gap for the respective group of myxomycetes (Borg Dahl et al. 2018, Yatsiuk et al. 2023). Build a phylogeny to test that the new taxon (i) represents a monophyletic group and (ii) does not branch within any other taxon. It is important to include in the analysis all accessions sequenced for related species.

(6) Avoid choosing an epithet already in use in any myxomycete species. This makes it easier to cope with future nomenclatural changes, which may include the transfer of the species into another genus. For the genus, avoid names already used in zoological nomenclature: this may cause problems after a possible change of the applicable Code from botanical to zoological nomenclature (Ronikier & Halamski 2018).

(7) Deposit voucher specimens in several public herbaria, to increase accessibility for further studies. Spores may be stored separately in tubes at 4°C; the data from ferns suggest this treatment to conserve nuclei and thus DNA for future molecular studies (Tang et al. 2023).

(8) Publish primary data about all specimens used for species characterization, such as occurrence data, photos, measurement tables, drawings, sequences, alignments, and trees, together with a formal description as links to openly accessible datasets. Primary data drastically increase the value of any publication, being a) excellent means for verification of presented hypotheses b) a valuable source for the subsequent researchers that might employ them to test other hypotheses, come from other research areas etc.

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Myxomycetes in metabarcoding data: from the tropics to the Arctic

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Keywords: biogeography, metabarcoding, neotropics, paleotropics

In fruit body-based surveys, myxomycetes have shown a trend of diversity highest in temperate regions and decreasing towards tropics (Schnittler et al., 2022). This trend is opposite to the diversity of the majority of other groups of organisms. However, it is still unknown whether the same holds true for the diversity of myxomycete assemblages in soil, at the level of trophic stages.

There is another long-standing question in myxomycete biogeography: to what extent are myxomycete species ubiquitous and how similar are myxomycete assemblages in different parts of the same climatic zone? The answer to this question is especially complicated due to large number of cryptic undescribed species in many common morphologically recognized species.

We will address these questions based on 18S rDNA metabarcoding data sets that encompass several regions in Eurasia from the Arctic to subtropics, as well as several sites in paleotropics and one in neotropics.

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Myxomycetes in the interior

Elizaveta Shchepina

Keywords: art, design, slime molds

Sometimes people who are not involved in science encounter a new, unfamiliar object for the first time and realize that there are people who study it. They often ask: "What benefit to humanity does your object of study provide?" Some ask this out of sincere curiosity, some out of a pragmatic and anthropocentric mindset. Such a question is often asked about myxomycetes as well. In response to this question, one can go into general explanations about how fundamental science works, or talk about the role of myxomycetes in ecosystems, and so on. These are all wonderful, correct and logical answers, but it is also possible to approach this question from an emotional standpoint and say: "First of all, myxomycetes are beautiful, and I'm going to show you that."

Other biological objects, such as plants and animals, often become the subjects of symbolism, illustrations and paintings that decorate interiors. Since they are generally accepted as "beautiful" and have thus become commonplace, no one has questions about why they are studied. Perhaps making a beautiful object like myxomycetes a familiar part of the human household and notions of aesthetics is also a way to raise awareness of them and their importance to people? With that idea in mind, I'm trying to create interior drawings of myxomycetes.

A long and winding road: my life with myxomycetes

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Keywords: career, life experiences, research.

During the first part of my academic career, I wasn't a "myxo person." In fact, I received my M.S. and Ph.D. degrees in plant (more specifically forest) ecology. My first exposure to myxos was a brief mention of the group in a lecture on fungi given in a botany course I took as an undergraduate. I don't remember anything from that lecture. However, I was given a proper introduction to these organisms in a graduate mycology course taught by Orson Miller. I was carrying out fieldwork related to my degree at the time, and I began noticing myxos in the forests I was studying. In 1982, I received a summer post-doc at the Mountain Lake Biological Station in southwestern Virginia. The post-doc was awarded for a project I had proposed to study the distribution and ecology of forest communities in the area around the Station, but I incorporated myxos into the project. The data I obtained yielded my first major papers on myxo ecology and ultimately set the stage for a Fulbright Award to India, my first NSF grant to study myxos, my first of many collecting trips throughout the world, the development of numerous productive collaborations with other scientists with an interest in studying myxos, the opportunity to mentor a series of graduate students who earned their degrees working with myxos, and being able to edit or write several books on myxos. This present is an overview of the long and winding road I traveled during my career. I hope it inspires the next generation of myxo people!

First records of bryophylous myxomycetes in the plane part of Ukraine

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Keywords: Bryophyta, molecular barcoding, phylogeny

Although many species of myxomycetes may form fruiting bodies on bryophytes, only small fraction of them seem to spend the whole life cycle of on this substrate, thus being considered as bryophylous. Only four species from this ecological guild were found in Ukraine: *Barbeyella minutissima*, *Colloderma oculatum*, *Diderma* (= *Lepidoderma*) *tigrinum*, and *Lamproderma columbinum*, collected by Helena Kremieniewska in the Eastern Carpathians in 1920–1930s (Krzemieniewska, 1934; Kryvomaz, Dudka, 2014). At the plane part of Ukraine truly bryophylous myxomycetes were never found.

As a result of the two-years-long monitoring of mossy logs of *Quercus robur*, situated in the Slobozhanskyi National Nature Park (50°06'25.2"N, 35°10'43.3"E) we made a repeated findings of three bryophylous species. These are *Diderma tigrinum*, collected 04 Jan 2023, *Colloderma oculatum*, collected 20 Nov 2021, 14 Oct 2022 and 02 Dec 2022, and the putatively new species of *Lamproderma*, collected 11 Aug 2022 and 14 Oct 2022. Nucleotide BLAST search of 18S rDNA and EF1a partial sequences of the latter species have shown 2.5% and 19.7% genetic distance from the nearest known sequences, respectively. Phylogenetic analysis disclosed the relation of *Lamproderma* sp. with another bryophylous species, *L. muscicola*. However, in *Lamproderma* sp. spores are 11–13 µm diam. and ornamented with clustered warts, while in *L. muscicola* they are 12–15 µm diam. and ornamented with evenly spaced spinules.

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Environmental DNA collection using a simple air sampler for taxonomic and phylogenetic studies of myxomycetes

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Keywords: eDNA, air sampler, low-cost

Myxomycetes are a diverse and ecologically important group of organisms that have attracted the attention of researchers in various fields. Taxonomy and phylogeny of myxomycetes have traditionally been studied using morphological and molecular methods, but recent developments in environmental DNA (eDNA) collection and analysis have provided a promising alternative for studying these organisms in their natural habitats.

In this talk, we present a simple and cost-effective air sampler device that we have developed for collecting eDNA of myxomycetes in the field. The device consists of a computer fan and a tissue acting as an air filter, which is used to capture airborne particles containing DNA. The principle of this device is to use the active airflow produced by the fan to filter out airborne particles containing DNA in the environment. We have tested this device in various natural habitats, including forests and grasslands, and have found it to be effective in capturing DNA from a wide range of different species.

The DNA collected by our device has the potential to be used to produce species occurrence maps and phylogenetic trees of the myxomycete communities in different habitats. It may also be possible to identify the fructification season of each species and detect hard-to-find species that would be difficult to detect using traditional sampling methods.

In this presentation, we will show the first results of our approach based on collecting air samples around a transect near Garmisch-Partenkirchen around June. Our results demonstrate the potential of eDNA collection using a simple air sampler device for studying myxomycetes and other organisms in their natural habitats. The use of this device can facilitate the collection of large amounts of eDNA data, which can be used to address a variety of ecological and evolutionary questions. We hope that our work will inspire other researchers to explore the use of eDNA in their own studies of myxomycetes and other organisms.

Intracellular fungal parasite of nivicolous myxomycetes

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Keywords: *Lamproderma*, *Diderma*, *Meriderma*, infection rate, host range

Transparent cyst-like bodies were found in fruiting bodies of nivicolous *Lamproderma echinosporum* and *Lamproderma* sp. (immatured) and reported as an unknown fungus in Cryptomycota, an early diversing lineage of Fungi by authors (Yajima et al. 2013). Although the nivicolous *Lamproderma* spp. are widely collected in the heavy snow regions in the world, there is no report on this fungus from the myxomycetes since then. In the initial report, this fungus was supposed to be specific to nivicolous myxomycetes and prefer cold regions. Recently, a new endoparasitic fungus on *Saccamoeba lacustris*, *Morellospora saccamoebae*, was described, which is closely related to our fungus (Corsaro et al. 2020). *M. saccamoebae* was found from the bark of a plane tree and cultivated within the amoeba at room temperature. This raises the question of why such a few records of this fungus were reported, even though the myxomycetes are “easily collectable/preferable amoebae” and adapt to various environments.

In the present study, we investigated the infection of this fungus to various species of the myxomycetes, not only the nivicolous but also summer and late-autumn species. The fungal infection was detected microscopic observations and PCR. Over 600 specimens of the fruiting bodies of myxomycetes were investigated, only detected within the 41 specimens of the nivicolous species at present. The nivicolous species of *Lamproderma*, *Diderma*, and *Meriderma* were recognized as the hosts. Although the infection of this fungus was easily recognized as white grains within the mature fruiting bodies in the initial report, the majority of the infected specimens in this report did not show such an obvious appearance. Only the spores harbored the cyst-like bodies of the fungus, and the appearances of the fruiting bodies were normal. This “normal appearance” of the fruiting body might lead a small number of reports of this fungus from the myxomycetes.

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Barcoding in species delimitation and otu-picking for dark-spored vs. bright-spored myxomycetes

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Keywords: barcoding gap, sequence similarity threshold

Barcoding and metabarcoding are powerful tools that bring benefits to ecological, taxonomical and conservational applications. In species delimitation, the concept of barcoding gap is used, e. g. sequences of the same species must be more similar to each other, than to the any of the close species. In eDNA studies, barcoding is used to distribute sequences into proxy units by applying universal sequence similarity thresholds across sequences from environmental samples (Collins and Cruickshank, 2013). Both applications found their place in myxomycetology during last decades (Clissmann et al., 2015; Leontyev et al., 2015; Shchepin et al., 2019). However, in view of the unique biology and immense genetic diversity of the group, both must be employed with caution. Previous investigations, reinforced with specimen-based taxonomy are required. We analyzed two datasets of 18S sequences representing unique ribotypes to i) test the barcoding gap ii) compare the otu-picking thresholds in two major subclasses of myxomycetes: Columellomycetidae (COL) vs Lucisporomycetidae (LUC). COL dataset included 203 sequences of 51 species; LUC, accordingly, comprised 320 sequences from 65 species. Mean intra- and interspecific distances in LUC dataset were significantly higher than in COL and mean interspecific distance was higher than intraspecific in both datasets ($p < 0.05$, 2-way ANOVA). The majority of species demonstrated a local barcoding gap. However, in both groups there were exceptions in cases of loose clusters of ribotypes (e.g. *Lamproderma ovoideum*, *Stemonitopsis hyperopta*) or closely related species (e.g. *Arcyria ferruginea-A. versicolor*, *A. denudata-A. major*), showing different evolutionary depths of species and/or taxonomical pitfalls. The search for the optimal OTU-picking threshold revealed that the optimal range for COL was 0.6-1.8 %, which is consistent with the previous larger-scale study (Borg Dahl et al., 2018). However, in LUC datasets optimal threshold range was broad and much higher: 1.7-8.5%. Minimal cumulative errors were high in any of the datasets, meaning that the perfect universal otu-picking threshold cannot be detected even within a subclass of myxomycetes.

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***Arcyria* and allied genera: taxonomic backbone, diversity and characters evolution.**

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Arcyria F. H. Wigg. is one of the largest genera of bright-spored myxomycetes, characterized by sporocarpic, usually stalked fruiting bodies (stalks filled with spore-like bodies) with evanescent peridium leaving a basal cup, and reticulate capillitium of hollow, copiously ornamented filaments (Robbrecht, 1974). Although the general outlines of the phylogeny of bright-spored myxomycetes have been recently drawn (García-Cunchillos et al., 2022), the genus *Arcyria* remained to be revised with broader taxa and geographical sampling.

Our study aims to (i) reconstruct the phylogeny of *Arcyria* relying on the more extensive sampling (ii) establish the taxonomic backbone for this group for subsequent taxonomic revision on the finer level (iii) reconstruct the evolution of morphological traits in *Arcyria* and analyze their value for taxonomic purposes. In the framework of the integrated taxonomy, we combined sequencing of two genes, 18S and *TEF1A*, with macro- and micromorphological studies, for over 350 specimens primarily attributed to 26 known morphospecies of *Arcyria* from herbarium collections and donations of citizen scientists worldwide.

Our results demonstrate that the genus *Arcyria* consists of two distinct clades, one well-supported, and the other very diverse in all senses, partly supported, although corroborating the results of previous works. We accordingly propose for discussion nomenclature changes that incorporate these findings. The majority of morphospecies included into this study appeared to be para- or polyphyletic taxa, with the extreme case of *A. cinerea*, but as well *A. affinis*, *A. afroalpina*, *A. denudata*, and *A. stipata*; or species complexes such as *A. obvelata*, *A. pomiformis*.

Morphological characters in *Arcyria* and allied taxa are subjected to selective pressure and probably gone through numerous gain and loss events in evolution. However, we demonstrate that visible coloration of fruiting bodies is to some degree correlated to a higher-level molecular phylogeny in *Arcyria*.

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